

AUTOMATED NON-DESTRUCTIVE ANALYSIS AND ADVANCED 3D DEFECT CHARACTERISATION FROM ULTRASONIC SCANS OF COMPOSITES.

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SUMMARY

With rapidly escalating usage of composite materials, production NDT data analysis may become the bottleneck preventing the required rise in production rates. Automated NDT analysis aims to release operators from the time-consuming analysis of all scans and focus their attention on non-compliant structures. The aim of 3D defect characterisation is to lighten the operator's decision-making burden.

Keywords: Ultrasonics, non-destructive, composites, characterisation, automation.

INTRODUCTION

At present the civil aerospace industry is undergoing its most rapid period of change in history, due to the large-scale move from metal to composite primary structures. This poses an immediate throughput challenge for the non-destructive testing (NDT) community on the production line where, initially, all composite primary structure will be inspected at manufacture. The background of composites NDT research in the UK has been covered recently in a review [1]. The current paper provides information in two new areas. Firstly, automated NDT analysis and sentencing to improve the throughput of the NDT stage in the composite manufacturing process; and secondly, 3D characterisation of composites, providing more information for the concession (disposition) process. 3D characterisation also allows large-scale measurement of material properties such as ply wrinkling (marceling) that have hitherto been inaccessible in the body of the material itself. In the future, structural designers may be able to specify acceptance criteria that can be varied with 3D structural location and thus remove weight from the structure that is currently only required because of the uncertainties associated with current bulk-property NDT measurements.

AUTOMATED NDT ANALYSIS AND SENTENCING

The NDT throughput problem for large-scale composite manufacturing in aerospace comprises two elements. The first, rapid acquisition of ultrasonic data over large and complex structures, has been largely solved by the use of automated or robotic acquisition systems, often using phased-array technology. But manufacturers are realising that the second element, analysis of the data and sentencing of the component, is likely to create a bottleneck in the production of key components. This is because of the sheer volume of data that must be processed by highly trained NDT operators – up

to a Terabyte of data per composite aircraft the size of a B787 or A350, each aircraft requiring several man-months to analyse the NDT data manually.

However, analysis of large-area data can be accelerated using automation such as Reference Scan Methodology to perform registration (alignment) in translation and rotation, followed by comparison with the stored reference-scan data. The reference scan represents a ‘perfect’ component and can be either simulated or generated from real data. Then the two data sets are compared automatically (see Figure 1), the resulting differences are detected, classified in terms of the cause (structural misalignment, noise, or a defect), and then various measurements are performed.

Figure 1. The C-scan (left) is registered in translation and rotation with the reference scan (centre) before being compared to produce the right-hand image in QinetiQ’s PinPoint™ software, followed by image comparison to highlight the impact damage.

These measurements are compared with the manufacturer’s localised acceptance criteria which are all stored as part of the reference scan. This process is used to filter out the large amount of data from ‘good’ structure so that the skilled operators can focus on the non-compliant parts of the structure, which may require referral for concession or repair. It is expected that Reference Scan Methodology could reduce the amount of data needing operator analysis, and therefore the NDT analyst manpower, by 90%. An additional benefit of rapid automated data analysis is that the component can rapidly be ‘passed’ and moved on from NDT to the next stage of the production line without occupying costly robotic inspection bays, thus allowing high production rates without the requirement for investment in duplication of capital equipment.

3D CHARACTERISATION OF COMPOSITES

Most of the critical material properties for carbon-fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP), such as void volume fraction (porosity) and fibre volume fraction (FVF) are currently measured indirectly using ultrasonic parameters related to bulk properties. These provide through-thickness averaged values of the measured ultrasonic parameter in the inspected region, which have to be related to material properties in a separate process, usually involving a skilled NDT operator for interpretation. Direct measurements of material properties would be of more use to structural designers and process-control managers, especially if they could be mapped as a function of 3D location. This would also allow future structural designers to vary the acceptance criteria on these parameters depending on the predicted stress at each location, resulting ultimately in lighter, less-conservative structures.

Through consultation with composite design engineers and materials scientists a list of composite material properties where accurate 3D measurements would be advantageous has been generated. These are:

- Fibre volume fraction (FVF) - including thick resin layers.
 - Porosity - distributed and layer.
 - Ply orientation.
 - In-plane fibre waviness.
 - Out-of-plane fibre wrinkling.
- } Fibre orientation

With full-waveform ultrasonic data, the acquisition and storage of which is now becoming commonplace for both production and in-service ultrasonic inspection, it is possible to map the above properties as 3D profiles. The analysis methods developed to extract each of the above 3D measurements from the composite's ultrasonic response are discussed after an explanation of the models developed to better understand ultrasonic propagation in layered fibre composites.

Modelling of ultrasonic propagation in composites

A multi-layer ultrasonic bulk wave propagation model, MLM-Propmat, has been developed to simulate the reflection and transmission responses of composite materials. A description of the model was presented recently by Mienczakowski et al [2]. Each layer is modelled as an effective medium using conventional mixture rules for the physical properties [3,4]. These have been augmented to include the frequency dependence of ultrasonic attenuation due to porosity in the resin, based on the scattering theories of Epstein and Carhart [5] and Allegra and Hawley [6].

The effects of porosity and other panel defects were investigated by using a flexible simulation of ultrasonic wave propagation through multi-layered structures. For the purposes of simulation it was assumed that a monolithic composite could be considered to contain multiple layers which could consist of resin alone, resin with fibres, or either of these with the inclusion of porosity. The model is essentially a transfer matrix formulation, and follows the earlier work of Freemantle [7]. For benchmarking purposes, a different and completely separate model was developed by the authors using similar mixture rules but a different software architecture and the ultrasonic attenuation due to porosity was calculated using the method described by Adler et al [8]. This second model was built into QinetiQ's ANDSCAN[®] waveform analysis software for easy comparison with experimental data. The ability to compare the two models proved invaluable during this programme.

The models have been used in the current programme to develop techniques to detect, localise and characterise flaws in composite materials. For example, Figure 2 shows the waveform and time-frequency plot simulated using the ANDSCAN-based model. It simulates a 32-ply structure (0.125 mm, 0.050" thick plies) with one porous ply (ply 10) and one thick resin layer (just above ply 18), inspected by a 10 MHz probe. It illustrates the markedly different frequency response from porosity and a thick resin layer.

Fibre-resin effects

Fibre-resin changes such as ply-spacing variations or fibre volume fraction (FVF) changes, are not visible in a back-wall echo amplitude C-scan because this parameter is insensitive to such anomalies. This is demonstrated in the back-wall echo C-scan in Figure 3 for a panel where gross changes in FVF at specific depths were created in the specimen by cutting triangles from one pre-preg ply and replacing in a different ply.

Figure 2. Modelled ultrasonic waveform and time-frequency plot for a 32-ply composite with porosity in ply 10 and thick resin layer at ply 18, 10 MHz probe.

Figure 3. Back-wall echo C-scan (right) for the 32-ply panel shown schematically (left) containing triangular ply cut-outs (-1 ply), and inserts (+1 ply). Lighter (yellow-red) areas on the C-scan indicate a reduced amplitude from the back wall, suggesting the ultrasound has been attenuated by porosity, but the ply cut-outs are not visible.

The back-wall C-scan shows very little contrast between the cut-out regions, but does show that some porosity has been created by the defect-manufacturing process. An alternative is to look at local changes in ultrasonic response of each volume element, building up a 3D profile like in Figure 4, showing a ply-spacing profile, which can be related to FVF if some assumptions are made about fibre distribution. In this case, the ply cut-outs are clearly visible in the section at the right depth.

Figure 4. Three perpendicular sections through a 3D profile of ply spacing (a parameter related to fibre volume fraction) for the panel shown in Figure 3 (left) and for a tape-lay-up composite panel (right) showing the butt line between tapes in a particular ply.

Also shown in Figure 4 is a similar 3D profile but for a tape lay-up panel, where the butt-line between tapes in a particular ply can be seen. This could be used to ensure that these butt-lines do not appear in a regular pattern or in a way that might cause an undesirable stress distribution or line of weakness.

Porosity

The requirement to measure porosity content dictates the main acceptance thresholds on bulk ultrasonic attenuation for production inspection of CFRP. Various attempts have been made to improve the quantification of porosity and these have been recently reviewed [11]. In order to develop a new 3D porosity measurement capability it was essential to use the above models to understand how the many factors affect the proposed porosity measurement method. Then a strategy had to be developed to separate or compensate for these effects. The authors have produced 3D profiles that qualitatively identify the 3D local distribution of porosity in a CFRP structure (see Figure 5), and the aim of the collaboration is to produce *quantitative* 3D information about porosity, both in production and in-service for repairs.

Figure 5. Sections through a 3D profile of a parameter related to local porosity for the panel shown schematically in Figure 3.

Fibre Orientation

The original work by the authors in 1993 [9], was to determine ply orientations (stacking sequence) non-destructively for a carbon-fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) skin. Eight years later, Hsu *et al* at Iowa State University [10] progressed the research further by using 2D Fast Fourier Transforms (2D-FFTs) to more accurately determine ply orientation – a process that was beyond the computational capabilities of the computer used in 1993. The authors have developed a variant of this 2D-FFT method and applied it to measurements of ply orientation, woven fabric analysis, in-plane waviness and out-of-plane wrinkling.

It is convenient to divide the measurement processes into two stages, the acquisition of the full-waveform ultrasonic data set for the component, and the subsequent analysis. At the acquisition stage the choice of inspection frequency, focal depth, aperture size and probe-to-sample separation and spatial sampling rate have a marked effect on the final results. The precise interaction of these parameters is complex and is not discussed fully in this paper, as the intention is to focus on the analysis of the data and the presentation of the results achievable.

Ply orientation (stacking sequence) analysis – StackScan™

For ply orientation (and in-plane waviness), acquisition must be optimised to provide good imaging of the fibre tows throughout the depth of the composite. Once acquired, a series of amplitude C-scans is produced, one for each depth within the composite. Visual analysis can be used to observe the ply orientations, but superior and automated results are achieved by analysing each C-scan using two-dimensional Fast Fourier Transforms (2D-FFT). The resultant frequency-space 2D-FFT output is used to generate an angular distribution for each C-scan, as shown in Figure 6.

This is repeated for the C-scan from each depth, the fibre tow orientations in which are then characterised by an angular distribution, and these distributions can be used to generate a ply stacking-sequence image. In the stacking-sequence image (Figure 7) the vertical axis relates to depth in the composite where zero depth, at the top of the image, corresponds to the front surface of the composite. Horizontal grey lines overlaid on the stacking sequence image denote the boundaries between plies. The horizontal axis of the image represents ply orientation in degrees. Each horizontal line in the image is an angular distribution at a particular depth; thus the orientation of each ply is indicated by the location of the vertical red line associated with a specific ply.

Figure 6: An example of an amplitude C-scan (left) , its 2D-FFT (middle) , and the calculated angular distribution (right).

Figure 7: Stacking sequence results generated from full-waveform ultrasonic data for two 16-ply CFRP Panels with correct lay-up (left) and incorrect lay-up (right).

The two stacking-sequence images shown in Figure 7 have been generated by analyzing the full-waveform ultrasonic data in the manner described, and are from two nominally identical CFRP panels containing 16 plies, with a thickness of 2.8 mm. One panel has a quasi-isotropic lay-up $[(-45/0/45/90)_2]_s$. The other has the lay-up $[(-45/90/45/0)_2]_s$ with the exception of the 11th ply which should be a 90-degree ply, but has been incorrectly set at -45-degrees. The ply angles have been appended to the right hand side of the images to aid visualisation of the stacking sequence.

With this technique it has been possible to measure the stacking sequence up to a depth of 5 mm in 8-ply/mm material, while for 4-ply/mm material it is possible to measure the stacking sequence in samples over 15 mm thick. This is a result of the lower inspection frequency required for thicker plies, resulting in lower attenuation. The analysis routines required to generate the stacking sequence images have been embedded in a software package called StackScan™.

Woven fabric analysis – Ply Fingerprinting™

A related use of the ply stacking-sequence tool is in the analysis of woven fabrics. In this case the angular distribution for each ply is more complicated as there are many angles associated with a particular weave type (see Figure 8). In the first instance this application allows for the weave type to be identified since each weave will have a characteristic angular-distribution ‘fingerprint’. As a result, the methodology by which woven fabrics is analysed within the StackScan™ software has been termed *Ply Fingerprinting™*.

Figure 8: Simulated ultrasonic images of 5 harness-satin weave with repeat patterns of [1] (top) and [2] (bottom) and the associated Ply Fingerprint™ (right) as measured by ANDSCAN®.

A further use of *Ply Fingerprinting*™ is to quantify distortion in woven fabrics and differences between warp and weft fibre-tow widths. For example, a plain weave fabric can be represented by a regular grid of nodes as shown in Figure 9, with key angles of 0°, 26°, 64°, 90° and 116°. In fabrics distorted by, for example, lateral or vertical compression or shear, these angles are altered. By measuring the characteristic angles, it should be possible to identify the type and severity of distortion the fabric has experienced.

Figure 9: Representation of a plain weave fabric as a grid, the associated angles of an undistorted fabric, and the angular changes associated with compression and shear.

An example stacking sequence generated from an 8-ply woven CFRP panel is presented in Figure 10. The angles of peaks are constant for the upper four plies, and are seen to change for the lower four plies, which are believed to be inverted relative to the upper plies so that the warp and weft are swapped. The fact that the angles are not the expected ones and that they shift below the centre line suggests that the warp and weft have different width fibre-tows.

Figure 10: Analysis of a plain weave fabric from full-waveform data, showing a distinction between the peak angles associated with the upper and lower plies.

In-plane fibre waviness

When performing stacking-sequence analysis the 2D-FFT from the entire C-scan is used to determine global fibre orientation within a ply. To characterize in-plane waviness, 2D-FFTs from small regions of each C-scan are analysed individually to determine the local fibre orientation, which is then used to populate a 2D output image where the colour scale is fibre angle (see Figure 11).

Figure 11: C-scan of wavy fibres in a single ply of CFRP (left), a quantitative 2D map of fibre orientation (middle) using the colour scale on the far right, and (right) a combined image superimposing these two images.

Figure 11 presents a C-scan from the depth of a single wavy ply in a CFRP panel, and the calculated fibre orientation is mapped as colour. In the fibre-orientation image green represents 45° fibres, yellows and reds are fibres greater than 45° and blues are fibres less than 45° . The combined image shows good agreement between the C-scan and the calculated angular distribution map.

Since a C-scan can be generated for each ply in the CFRP panel it is possible to produce a 3D data set of fibre orientation angles, indicating the 3D profile of waviness. For a non-wavy composite panel the fibre orientation C-scans should be constant in colour since the fibres are at a consistent angle at all locations at that depth. When viewing a cross-section through the 3D profile, bands of colour would be seen, corresponding to the plies. An example produced from a real CRRP panel with a $[(-45/0/45/90)_2]_s$ lay-up, in which these features are observed, is shown in Figure 12. In this example, there appears to be some out-of-plane wrinkling causing irregular boundaries between the plies. Quantifying this out-of-plane wrinkling (or marceling) is the subject of the next section.

Figure 12: Representation of a 3D fibre waviness data set showing a C-scan of a 90° ply (green), and two cross-sections showing 90° , -45° , 0° and $+45^\circ$ degree plies.

Out-of-plane ply wrinkling

For out-of-plane ply wrinkling the ultrasonic acquisition needs to be optimised to generate B-scans suitable for analysis. The probe needs to be sensitive to ultrasound reflected from wavy plies, thus the choice of aperture size and probe-to-sample separation become important. Once B-scans that image the ply waviness have been generated from the full-waveform data set, each one is analysed for its local angular

content. This is achieved by obtaining 2D-FFTs from small regions of each B-scan and using the measured local angle to generate a ply-wrinkling scan in which colour represents ply angle. An example output from this process is shown in Figure 13 in which a single B-scan from a real 72-ply 18-mm thick structure is shown.

Figure 13: B-scan (left) showing a wrinkle in an 18mm thick CFRP panel and the quantitative 2D map of the wrinkle (middle) using the calibrated colour scale (far right). The combined image (right) overlays these two images.

As with the in-plane fibre waviness, it is possible to produce a 3D profile of out-of-plane ply wrinkling since a B-scan image can be generated for each horizontal and vertical plane in the ultrasonic scan. An example for a simulated wrinkle is shown in Figure 14 together with the results of automated sizing of the wrinkle volume and measurement of its wavelength and maximum angular distortion. In Figure 15 the same 3D processing has been applied to the wrinkled specimen shown in Figure 13.

CONCLUSIONS

A rapid automated method for analysis of NDT data is presented, allowing NDT operators to focus on characterising defects. Most critical material properties, such as porosity, are currently measured indirectly using ultrasonic parameters related to bulk properties. Direct measurements of material properties would be of more use, especially if mapped as a function of 3D location. This would allow designers to vary acceptance criteria based on the predicted stress at each location, resulting ultimately in lighter structures. This paper gives examples of quantitative 3D profiling of composite material properties including porosity, fibre volume fraction, in-plane waviness and out-of-plane wrinkling.

Figure 14. 3D out-of-plane-wrinkle analysis for a simulated wrinkle, including full 3D sizing of the wrinkle volume, the wavelength of the wrinkle and the severity - the maximum ply angle.

Figure 15. 3D out-of-plane wrinkle analysis for the specimen shown in Figure 13.

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